

Evaluation of Facebook Translation Service (FTS) in Translating English Covid-19 Facebook Posts Into Arabic in Terms of TAUS Adequacy and Fluency

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March ,2017</p> <p>Accepted: June , 2017</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20681012</p> <p>Keywords : Facebook Translation Service (FTS), FTS adequacy and Fluency, English into Arabic Translation during Covid-19, Facebook Translation, Covid-19.</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to verify the capacity of Facebook Translation Service in translating English Facebook posts into Arabic in terms of two criteria: adequacy and fluency in line with the Translation Automation User Society (TAUS) scales. To ensure consistency and objectivity as recommended by TAUS creators, six evaluators, native speakers of Arabic and near-native speakers of English, rated the same data on each scale. The evaluators were acquainted with fluency and adequacy scales along with MT limitations and potentials. Once the corpus was uploaded and sent to the evaluators using TAUS tools, they had to assign scores online on 1-4 rating scales. Then, each report was displayed online on TAUS reports tool. Evaluators' responses were similar responses were combined in thematic categories and were calculated to obtain frequencies and percentages. The study found that FTS provided fluent with highest percentage of the scale good equal to 3 on a scale from 1 to 4, where the output is assessed as flowing smoothly with minor linguistic errors. Moreover, FTS succeeded in generating an adequate output with the highest percentage of responses as 'most' equal to 3 on a scale from 1 to 4, where almost the full meaning of the source is deemed to be transferred in the target language. This study is useful since it highlights the role of Facebook Translation service in translating, educating the public and fighting Covid-19. Consequently, such research would encourage the use and research on the potentiality of MT and FTS in dealing with abrupt crises, such as Covid-19.</i></p>

Introduction

Translation is the medium of human communications. It bridges the gap between human communities and ensures the best way of communicating among global communities. Nowadays, the world is facing the most frightening Coronavirus (Covid-19) outbreak in the last decade. The health authorities, international Health Organizations, political leaders, healthcare providers and the public have social media sites at their disposal. They post information regarding Covid-19 daily. The flow of social media posts about Covid-19 is unprecedented, and would be beyond the capacity of human translation, let alone an economically viable proposition to have them translated by humans. During lockdowns around the globe, Machine Translation (MT) helped to translate such posts into Arabic. [Kh \(2020\)](#) states, "The challenge is how to communicate rapidly changing data across language borders so that essential information is not lost in translation". In this regard, [Kh \(2020\)](#) goes as far as stating that machine translation is a strong ally in the fight against Covid-19.

Social media sites have become popular among young Arabs who tend to use them daily. [Statista \(2020\)](#) shows that Facebook is the most popular social media site in the Middle East with 200 million daily users, representing almost 70% of Middle East population. Facebook has translation service, which offer translation for more than 80 languages.

Facebook wide use makes it necessary to evaluate the content and verify its effectiveness and limitations to the end users. English ranks as the top language of social media with 25.3% of internet content, while Arabic content represents a mere 4.8%. This means that many Arab Facebookers will be exposed to posts written in English with some able to read and understand English, and a large portion of those who are not competent in English. Facebook has been offering their own translation service since 2011, FTS.

Users can easily activate the translation service on their profiles in two ways. Firstly, the users can click on top right hand of their page and select setting and privacy, then choose language and region. After that, users have to click on the language into which they would like to have posts translated to. The current study scrutinizes FTS in terms of adequacy and fluency in rendering English posts into Arabic during the Covid-19 lockdown.

Machine Translation

Machine Translation (MT) is the study of the computer's systems or online applications in transferring the Natural Languages from one language into another. [Microsoft Translator \(2020\)](#) shows that MT systems are "applications

or online services that use machine-learning technologies to translate large amounts of text from and to any of their supported languages. The service translates a “source” text from one language to a different “target” language”. The availability of such online systems for free or at low costs make it necessary to verify the effectiveness of MT systems in dealing with natural languages especially with the languages belong to different families such as English and Arabic.

Translation has been integrated into technology thanks to the giant technological progress of the last 70 years, starting with the first successful MT project at the University of Georgetown in 1954 as a result of collaboration between Georgetown University and International Business Machines (IBM). [Hutchins \(2010, p.2\)](#) indicated that the success of the first experiment “attracted a great deal of media attention in the United States. Although the system had little scientific value, its output was sufficiently impressive to stimulate the large scale funding of MT research in the USA and to inspire the initiation of MT projects elsewhere in the world and notably in the USSR”. [Almahasees \(2020, p.33\)](#) shows that 1980 is considered a flagship moment of MT with new developments emerging whilst “more dramatic development took place in MT in the 1990 since computers became more powerful with much higher storage capabilities”. This crowned with the invention of the internet, a source of translation for the general public ([Gaspari and Hutchins 2007, pp-199-206](#)). Automatic translation tools available on the Internet translate billions of documents daily, which would take human translators months. Whereas MT service was not free in the early history of the Internet, nowadays, we have a set of MT platforms that provide translation service for free such as Google Translate, Microsoft Translator, FTS and others. [Rachmat \(2018\)](#) states, “Machine Translation (MT) is being deployed for a range of use-cases by millions of people on a daily basis. Google Translate and FaceBook provide billions of translations daily across many language”.

Facebook Translation

Historically, [Amendola \(2012\)](#) showed that Facebook, firstly, used Google Translate service to translate comments into 50 languages. Facebook launched its first Translation Service in 2011, called In-line Translation Facebook Tool ([Singh, 2011](#)). [Fernandes \(2011\)](#) states, “After Google integrated the “translate” feature into its social network, which allows users to translate posts and comments into 50 different languages, Facebook, as usual has followed the footprints of Google+, and quietly announced the launch of “translate” button – powered by Microsoft’s Bing”, setting itself apart from Google. [White \(2011\)](#) described the first Facebook Translation tool as “Facebook has quietly introduced a new tool that makes instant inline language translations appear with a single click”. For instance, if a non-Spanish user on a Facebook public page, stumbles upon a comment in Spanish, then he/she will see a Translate button next to it. A single click on the button will translate the comment into English. FTS works on individual posts on Facebook and not on users’ profiles yet, including comments. Currently, FTS offers translation service for 89 languages and they will continue to add more languages.

FTS adopted phrase to phrase MT approach, thus translating whole sequences of words of differing lengths. In 2017, Mark Zuckerberg, the founder of Facebook, explained that translation is the best mean to connect human globally “Understanding someone’s language brings you closer to them, and I’m looking forward to making universal translation a reality. To help us get there faster, we’re sharing our work publicly so that all researchers can use it to build better translation tools”. In the same year, Facebook research team developed a new MT approach using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) allowing to translate languages more accurately (read: increase quality on a BLEU scale) and up to nine times faster than the traditional recurrent neural networks (RNNs). [Zuckerberg \(2017\)](#) described the new MT approach as “Today we’re publishing research on how AI can deliver better language translations. With a new neural network, our AI research team was able to translate more accurately between languages, while also being nine times faster than current methods”, a superior speed confirmed by [Gehring et al. \(2017\)](#). [Facebook AI engineering \(2017\)](#) have shown that “CNNs have been very successful in several machine learning fields, such as image processing. However, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are the incumbent technology for text applications and have been the top choice for language translation because of their high accuracy”.

In the late of 2019, Facebook research has declared new advances in NLP, which boost the accuracy of Facebook Translation. They have also introduced a new self-supervised pretraining approach, RoBERTa, that surpassed all existing Natural Language Understanding (NLU) systems on several language comprehension tasks. They have also collaborated with New York University (NYU), DeepMind Technologies, and the University of Washington (UW) to promote their future research ([Facebook Research Intelligence, 2019](#)).

In a first study on Facebook Translation evaluation, it evaluated Facebook translation service in handling low-resources languages: Lao, Kazakh, Haitian, Oromo, and Burmese. They evaluated the translation of English posts into these languages. They implemented different strategies: LASER, back-translations, self-training, multilingual modeling, to improve the translation from English to low source languages “For instance, Sinhala to English and Nepali to English translations on Facebook have improved from “useful,” which are just accurate enough to understand the meaning, to “good,” which generates full meaning but may have typos or grammatical errors” ([Facebook AI, 2019](#)).

The study is mainly concerned with Facebook translation of English posts related to Covid-19 released by International organizations such as WHO, political leaders, medical specialists and the general public. The study

aims to verify the efficiency of FTS in translating posts from English into Arabic and provides constructive feedback about the degree of fluency and adequacy of FTS and whether FTS is considered a reliable source of information or not.

Machine Translation Evaluation

MT systems Evaluation (MTE) is crucial to the development of MT systems. [Almahasees \(2020, p.48\)](#) shows that the evaluation of MT is central to determine the effectiveness and performance of MT systems. Machine Translation Evaluation is essential to all end-users: researchers, designers and users to select the best system to use [EuroMatrix \(2007\)](#). In similar way, the development of Mt systems depends on the evaluation of MT systems, limitations and strengths of the systems. MT evaluation sheds light on the capacity of the system what can the system do or cannot do. [Koby et al. \(2014, p.416\)](#) emphasize that the evaluation of MT system “demonstrates accuracy and fluency required for the audience and purpose and complies with all other specifications negotiated between the requester and provider, taking into account end-user needs”.

Many evaluation methods have been used over the history of MTE. The first MT evaluation dated back to 1954 to assess the ability to translate 250 words from Russian into English. They succeeded in translating this small number of words from Russian into English. The success of the experiment attracted a lot of funding. Consequently, in 1962 the first committee, the Automatic Language Processing Advisory Committee (ALPAC), was formed to evaluate. They found that there it is not worthy to spend more money on useful MT system. The report ended with nine recommendations to evaluate MT, three of them encouraged to do further research on MT systems ([ALPAC, 1966](#)).

MT systems have achieved high performance close to human accuracy [Hassan et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Wu et al. \(2016\)](#). shown that MT systems ‘performance have achieved near human level performance. However, many studies have highlighted the shortcomings of MT in dealing with Natural language processing (NLP). have indicated that the main challenge of MT is having large parallel corpora. However, these corpora are not available in all NL [Koehn et al. \(2017\)](#), [Isabella et al. \(2017\)](#), [Sennrich et al. \(2015\)](#). There are very limited parallel corpora for the majority of language pairs. On the other hand, most of previous studies depend on monolingual corpora in each language [Lample \(2018\)](#), [Artex et al. \(2018\)](#). According to [Lample et al. \(2018, p.1\)](#), the success of the previsions of MT research is to “the use of inferred bilingual dictionary”. Moreover, indicated that the success of the previous studies is to the use of model training in sequence to sequence systems [Bahdanan et al. \(2015\)](#), [Sutskever et al. \(2014\)](#) [Vincent et al. \(2008\)](#). Previous studies have adopted back translation strategy in supervising i.e. generating inputs to train the target models and vice versa. Despite the fact that there are many methods designed to evaluate, there is still no generally accepted methodology for evaluating MT systems. Yet, MT needs evaluating. Evaluating MT can be done manually and automatically [Sennrich et al. \(2015\)](#).

To assess MT system, there are three stages to evaluate the performance and efficiency of the systems: firstly, the design of the system, secondly the development of the system and thirdly the evaluation of the system by potential customers ([Hutchins \(1992\)](#)). With regards to the third point, MT evaluation was divided into three categories. The first is adequacy which is used to assess the end user’s needs, such as readability and costs. The second is diagnostic evaluation, where the designers and developers examine the output of MT and its relevance to the input. The third is the performance evaluation in order to assess the systems’ performance in specific areas to assist the developers and the designers of the system [Hirschman and Thompson \(1997\)](#).

MT could be evaluated manually and automatically [Chan \(2014\)](#) and [Almahasees \(2018\)](#). [Almahasees \(2018, p.1\)](#) states, “Manual evaluation assesses the usability of the systems via human participants in terms of Error analysis [...]; automatic evaluation evaluates MT outputs in terms of texts similarity to a referenced translation”. Similarly, MT evaluation has two aspects: intrinsic and extrinsic. The former highlights the language quality, while the former highlights the capacity and efficiency of the system. He also adds that there are two ways to evaluate MT output: automatic and manual evaluation. Automatic evaluation relies on the usage of metrics that could approximate the similarity between the output and the human referenced translation without human interventions, while manual evaluation depends on human evaluators to assess and rank MT output [Chan \(2014, p.221\)](#). [EuroMatrix \(2007\)](#) sums up the advantages of automatic evaluation as fast and cheap: there is no need for bilingual speakers, it requires minimal human labor and can be used as an ongoing evaluation process during the design of the system.

MT could be evaluated automatically in terms of Edit-Distance metrics, Precision and Recall, F-Measure and Word Order. [Przybocki et al. \(2006, p.2039\)](#) indicated that Edit Distance evaluates MT in terms of additions, omissions, substitutions, which are the requirements for adequate output. Precision and Recall evaluates the degree of n-gram matching between MT and human translation based on referenced translation, such as BLEU and NIST. The F measure is used to measure the overall quality performance. The word order counts the word order sequence between the source sentence and the output of MT. [Stephens \(2014, p.10\)](#) reminds us why BLEU is the most popular metrics among researchers:

one of the reasons why the metric is popular in the community seems to be for its simplicity for MT developers at least. Another reason why BLEU is widely used is that it has the best correlations with

human judgments of translation quality. It estimates the similarity between the translated sentence and the referenced sentence.

In fact, automatic evaluation has some advantages, but its shortcomings outweigh its advantages. Automatic evaluation assesses the text similarity between the output and the referenced human translation. It does not look for the meaning transference from the ST to TT, which are fundamental requirements for accuracy in translation. Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) looks for n-gram similarity not meaning (Tatman, 2014). [Reiter \(2018\)](#) further argues that BLEU evaluation is quite difficult to assess the meaning rather than text similarity. Moreover, the Translation Automation User Society ([TAUS, 2019](#)) agrees that automatic evaluation could provide one side of quality, which could not reflect the genuine quality of MT output. For these reasons and others, the current study adopts manual methods in evaluating MT output holistically in terms of adequacy and fluency scales provided by TAUS, rather than automated evaluations using BLEU for instance.

In fact, manual evaluation of MT is considered as golden standard to evaluate MT and cannot be overwhelmed by automatic evaluation. Manual evaluation of MT could be done in terms of quality assessment, translation ranking, error analysis, information extraction, comprehension test and post editing. Translation ranking results provides the ender users with the degree of the output intelligibility.

In the same vein, [TAUS \(2015\)](#) developed several tools for MT quality evaluation. They offered these tools on their website to conduct MT evaluation in terms of adequacy and fluency. The adequacy tool enables the evaluators to assess the output based on 1-4 rating scales to verify how much of the meaning is contained in the target text translation as shown in Table 1 & 2.

Table 1. Fluency Rating Scale ([TAUS,219](#))

Adequacy Rating Scales		
4	Everything	All of the meaning in the source is contained, no more, no less
3	Most	Almost all the meaning in the source is contained in the translation.
2	Little	Fragments of the meaning in the source are contained in the translation.
1	None	None of the meaning in the source is contained in the translation.

On the other hand, [TAUS \(2015\)](#) also provides a fluency tool to evaluate MT output in terms of structural rules as accepted by native speakers of the TL. Fluency evaluates MT output in terms of 1-4 rating scales.

Table 2. Fluency Rating Scale ([TAUS, 2019](#))

Fluency Rating scales		
4	Flawless	Refers to a perfectly flowing text with no errors.
3	Good	Refers to a smoothly flowing text even when a number of minor errors are present.
2	Disfluent	Refers to a text that is poorly written and difficult to understand.
1	Incomprehensible	Refers to a very poorly written text that is impossible to understand.

The present study aims to verify the best results of MT outputs in terms of adequacy and fluency scales provided by TAUS. The study has adopted TAUS since it provides a constructive feedback of the Facebook Machine Translation. Such feedback helps the system' developers to improve the efficiency of the systems and provide the users with insights about how much is the FTS is adequate and fluent.

Literature Review

As discussed above that MTE is essential in evaluating MT output to provide the end users with feedback about the strength and limitations of the systems. Facebook is the most prominent social media sites globally. It is also classed as the most popular social media site in the Arab region. Therefore, Facebook became a major source of information for the majority of Facebookers during the Covid-19 outbreak. No research to date has been conducted to evaluate the efficiency of Facebook Translation in rendering English posts into Arabic in general and Covid-19 in particular.

[Khasawneh et al. \(2020\)](#) have conducted a descriptive study on medical student in Jordan to assess knowledge, attitude, perceptions, and precautionary measures toward Covid-19 among a sample of student in Jordan. They

have found that 83.4% used social media sites as their preferred source of information regard Covid-19. Moreover, [Alzoubi et al. \(2020\)](#) have conducted another study in Jordan to assess knowledge, practice and attitude of university students regardless of their majors. They have found that the source of information for the University students are social media, internet and television. No significant difference was noticed between medical and non-medical colleges students on the sources of their information.

On the other hand, [Garza \(2020\)](#) has shown the social media sites have become a useful tool in confronting the crisis and connecting people together during the crisis. Moreover, public health experts have used social media sites as to educate the public about the effects of COVID-19 and with discuss Covid-19 with specialists. The acceleration in the digital life changes the way of approaching the health information. She shows public health experts will use social media sites to spread correct information regard health problems [Zakrzewski \(2020\)](#). [Ouyang \(2020\)](#) shows that Facebook becomes the source of discussion and information exchange for 100,000 health care providers regarding the Covid-19 outbreak.

Social media sites have become platforms for survival against social isolation during the Covid-19 to “help people avoid the detrimental effects of social isolation during this pandemic” ([Etzioni, 2020](#)), with Facebook playing a major role as well ([Goldstein 2020](#)). Social networks usage has rocketed covering different aspects of our life, medical, geography and business growth. Facebook has been used widely during COVID-19 as a platform for business, charity, and community service ([Goldstein, 2020](#)). [Heilweil \(2020\)](#) goes as far as suggesting that social media sites during the crisis preached religion to the followers and provided a form of religious instruction and support. On the other hand, Social media shows how social networks become the platform for sharing hurtful messages for people of China. They blamed China as a source of the crisis. ([Wong, 2020](#)). However, Facebook and other social media clamped down the spread of fake news concerning Covid-19 and fake news ([Scott, 2020](#)).

Methodology

The study evaluates the effectiveness FTS in providing adequate and fluent outputs for English posts related to Coronavirus into Arabic. It provides an answer to the following question: To what extent FTS is capable in providing adequate and fluent translation for English Covid-19 posts into Arabic? To answer this questions, six evaluators evaluated the output of FTS in terms of the above TAUS adequacy and fluency scales.

The corpus of the study consists of 300 English posts related Covid-19, collected over March and April 2020, the peak months of the pandemic. The posts were selected from various Facebook pages that belonged to political leaders, healthcare providers, medical specialists and the public. To ensure consistency and objectivity as recommended by TAUS creators, six evaluators, native speakers of Arabic and near-native speakers of English, rated the same data on each scale. The evaluators were acquainted with fluency and adequacy scales along with MT limitations and potentials. Once the corpus was uploaded and sent to the evaluators using TAUS tools, they had to assign scores online on 1-4 rating scales. Then, each report was displayed online on TAUS reports tool. Data were analyzed using SPSS Statistics to get Pearson interrater agreement among evaluators in ranking the output at two different times. The results showed that there is a high inter-rater reliability among the raters.

Table 3. Interrater correlation

Rater	Statistics	Fluency	Adequacy
Rater 1	R	.947**	.969**
	P.	.000	.000
Rater 2	R	.973**	.936**
	P.	.000	.000
Rater 3	R	.931**	.967**
	P.	.000	.000
Rater 4	R	.839**	.782**
	P.	.000	.000
Rater 5	R	.976**	.867**
	P.	.000	.000
Rater 6	R	.944**	.985**
	P.	.000	.000

The above table shows Interrater correlation using Person correlation between first and second evaluation for each rater, resulting in a statistically significant strong correlation between first and second evaluation for each rater.

Results and Discussion

Fluency

The following example illustrates how FTS translated World Health Organization (WHO) Covid-19 instructional post into Arabic.

Example 1

Source Text: Many people are making great sacrifices to stay home and protect their health and that of others from COVID-19.

FTS output: 19-كوفيد-19 الكثير من الناس يقدمون تضحيات كبيرة للبقاء في المنزل وحماية صحتهم وصحة الآخرين من كوفيد-19
 alkthyrmnalnasyqdmwntdhyatkbyrhllbqa' fyalmnzlwhmayshthmwshhalakhrynmmn kwfyd-19

Back translation: many people are offering great sacrifices to stay home and protect their health and that of others from Covid-19.

This example shows how FTS rendered the English WHO post into Arabic. The analysis showed that FTS rendered the posts fluently. Moreover, four of the raters gave the above example a rate of 4, flawless, while two of them ranked it as 3, Good. The analysis showed that FTS provided an intelligible and fluent output.

Example 2

Source Text: Now, anyone returning from overseas is being forced into quarantine for 14 days when they arrive back in Australia. This is mostly occurring in hotels, and at Government expense.

FTS output: الان، اي شخص عائد من الخارج يجبر الى الحجر الصحي لمدة 14 ايام عندما يعود الى استراليا. يحدث هذا في الغالب في الفنادق، وعلى نفقة الحكومة.

alan, ay shkhs 'ea'edmnalkharjyibr ala alhjralshylmdh 14 ayam 'endmay'ewd ala astralya.
 yhdthhdafyalghalbfyalfnadq, w'elanfqhalhkwmh.

Back Translation: Now, anyone returning from abroad is being forced into quarantine for 14 days when they return to Australia. This is mostly occurring in hotels, and at Government expense.

The above example shows how FTS rendered into Arabic a Facebook post of Mark McGowan, Premier of Western Australia, regarding the quarantine for arrivals to Australia. The analysis showed that the raters rated the post in a balanced way. Three of raters rated the output as flawless, where the post is perfectly translated. Moreover, three of them ranked FTS output as Good, where the sentence is fluently translated despite minor errors. In fact, these minor errors did not inhibit the intelligibility of the text.

Figure 1: FTS Fluency

The above chart illustrates the degree of fluency obtained by FTS in providing fluent translation for English posts related to Covid-19 into Arabic. The highest fluency scale goes for **good** among the six evaluators with a percentage of 55.33%, where FTS output is easily understood without difficulty even when a number of minor errors are present. The lowest scale goes for incomprehensible scale, where the output is poor and impossible to understand which is equal to 0.67%. The first and second raters had similar evaluation. They indicated that FTS output is held between **good** where the output has minor errors with 55.33% and **flawless** with 29.67%, a perfect output with no errors. The other four raters ranked FTS as **good**, followed by **Flawless** and then **disfluent**, where the text is poorly written and difficult to understand. According to the raters, FTS is mostly adequate in conveying Source Text (ST) to Target Text (TT) where there is a target side translation grammatically well informed, without spelling errors and experienced as using natural/intuitive language by a native speaker.

Adequacy**Example 3**

Source Text: The conclusion I reached is that the Government should end the lockdown after Easter and return to a mitigation strategy, with self-quarantining limited to those most at risk" writes Toby Young.

FTS Output: الاستنتاج الذي توصلت اليه هو انه ينبغي للحكومة اثناء الاغلاق بعد عيد الفصح والعودة الى استراتيجية التخفيف، مع الحجر الصحي الذاتي، يقتصر على اولئك الاكثر عرضة للخطر، يكتب توبي يونغ.

alasntajaldytwsltalyhhwanhynbghyllhkwmhanha' alaghlaqb'ed 'eydalfshwal'ewdh ala astratyjyhaltkhfyf, m'ealhjralshyaldaty, yqtsr 'elaawl'ekalakthr 'erdhllkhtr, ykbtwbywnggh.

Back Translation: The conclusion I reached is that the government should end the lockdown after Easter and returned to mitigation strategy, with self-quarantining limited to those at most risks, writes Toby Young.

This example shows how FTS rendered the Telegraph Facebook Posts into Arabic. The results showed that the source text meaning is contained in the output translation. The four raters rated the FTS output as Most, where almost all the meaning in the source text is contained in the translation. However, two raters gave a scale of 4 Everything. The current study concurs with the last rating, everything, that all the information contained in the source text is found in the target output.

Example 4

Source Text:When the world's doctors come together, amazing things can happen. We're all hopeful that plasma therapy can help treat COVID-19.

I'm glad Bloomberg Philanthropies can play our part to support Arturo Casadevall's research.

FTS Output:

عندما يجتمع اطباء العالم معا، يمكن ان تحدث اشياء مذهلة. نحن جميعا نامل ان العلاج بالبلازما يمكن ان يساعد في علاج كوفيد-19.

انا سعيد ان Bloomberg Philanthropies يمكن ان يلعب دورنا لدعم ابحاث ارتورو كاسادفال

'endmayjtm'eatba' al'ealmm'ea, ymkn an thdthashya' mdhlh. nhnjmy'eanaml an al'elajbalblazmaymkn an ysa'edfy 'elaj kwfyd-19.

ymkn an yl'ebdwrnald'emabhathartwrwkasadfal Bloomberg Philanthropies anas'eyd an

Back Translation: When the world's doctors come together, amazing things can happen. We are hopeful that Plasma thereby can help cure Covid-19. I happy that Bloomberg Philanthropies can take part in supporting Arturo Casadevall's research.

The example shows how FTS transferred the English post into Arabic. The six assessors ranked the output differently. Four of them rated it as Most, while the other two raters ranked it as Little. The study correlates with the four raters that almost all the meaning in the source text is contained in the translation. However, the study indicates that keeping the noun 'Bloomberg Philanthropies' untranslated does not inhibit the intelligibility of the text

Figure 2: Adequacy Scales

The above chart shows the degree of adequacy obtained by FTS in providing adequate translation for English Facebook Posts related to Covid-19 into Arabic. The analysis showed that the highest adequacy scale goes for *most* scale with a percentage of 47%, where almost of source text meaning is contained in the target text, while the lowest scale goes for *none*, none of the meaning is contained in the translation which is equal to 5.33%. The

six raters had similar views that most of the outputs are scaled as *most*, followed by *everything*, all the meaning of the source text is contained in the translation, and then little in the third rank and None with lowest rate. The below chart illustrates FTS performance based on TAUS adequacy and Fluency as follows.

Figure 3: FTS Fluency and Adequacy Performance

The above chart illustrates the ratings of fluency and adequacy obtained by FTS in rendering English Facebook posts related to Covid-19 into Arabic. The analysis showed that the highest degree of adequacy achieved by FTS Most with a percentage of 46.33 followed by Everything and then Little and None, indicating that almost of ST meaning is contained in the TL. Similarly, FTS the highest degree of fluency achieved by FTS is Good, where FTS succeeded in providing Fluent output with minor grammatical categories, followed by Flawless, Disfluent and then Incomprehensible. These two degree indicate the FTS could provide fluent and adequate translation to the end users.

The results of the study have indicated that Facebook conduct rigorous research to ensure the best translation quality for the end users. The study has shown that FTS has achieved a high degree of fluency starting with *good* scale, followed by *flawless*, *disfluent* and *incomprehensible*. Concerning the study has shown that FTS achieved a higher degree of adequacy starting with *most*, followed by *everything*, *little* and *none*. These results agree with [Zuckerberg \(2017\)](#) that Facebook introduced Neural Machine Translation (NMT) to provide an accurate translation for the end users. Moreover, the study confirms the findings by [Mohammad and Benvie \(2018\)](#) that NMT introduction enhances the accuracy and the speed of MT across languages. The study correlates with [Facebook AI \(2019\)](#) that self-training, back-translations, self-training, multilingual modeling could improve Facebook translation accuracy across human languages.

Conclusion

This research is the first research to fill a gap in the literature about the FTS degree of adequacy FTS in contributing to translate the English Facebook posts related to Covid-19 into Arabic. It provides useful data on FTS adequacy and fluency criteria.

Overall, Facebook translation service obtained a high degree of adequacy and fluency. This is because may FTS is trained well to deal with Arabic content. More importantly, we could benefit from FTS with Human Assisted Machine Translation (HAMT), in which a computer system does most of the translation, appealing in case of difficulty to a human translator for post editing services. Therefore, FTS helps in fighting Covid-19 since it facilitates the process of information exchange. Moreover, the study recommends further studies to conduct diachronic evaluation for FTS output over a period of time since the current study is limited to assess FTS output during Covid-19 outbreak in Jordan. Despite the fact that FTS achieved a higher degree of adequacy and fluency scales, but the current analysis does not cover all genres and therefore there is a lack of integrative evaluation studies that paved the research for the holistic analysis and the error analysis studies. The FTS is still far from reaching fully adequate and fluent translation of a quality obtained by human translators.

LIMITATION AND STUDY FORWARD

This study has some limitations as it investigates the adequacy and fluency of Facebook Translation Service during COVID-19 on a particular post, namely Covid-19, from the instructors' perspective, within a defined timeframe (post COVID-19 era), and geographical context (Jordan) to answer three research questions. Consequently, further research will be necessary to examine the adequacy and fluency of FTS in other fields and

different timeframes. That the current study focuses on the period of the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is recommended that other researchers examine the long-term adequacy and fluency of FTS in all fields. It is recommended that other researchers conduct similar research on the adequacy and fluency of FTS in translating from English into their languages at different situations.

8. References

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